

CHARACTER ASSOCIATION AND PATH ANALYSIS FOR YIELD AND YIELD COMPONENTS IN GROUNDNUT (*Arachis hypogaea* L.)D. D. Latthe^{1*}, Dr. P. B. Wadikar², A.R. Jadhav³, V.A. Kulkarni⁴^{1,3&4}Department of Genetics and Plant Breeding, College of Agriculture, Latur, Maharashtra, India²Associate Professor, Department of Genetics and Plant Breeding, College of Agriculture, Latur, Maharashtra, India

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Abstract

Groundnut is an important oilseed crop grown in Maharashtra and India during kharif (rainfed). The study was undertaken to estimate correlation coefficient and direct and indirect effects by path coefficient analysis for pod yield per plant among the 30 groundnut genotypes at Experimental Farm, College of Agriculture, Latur, Maharashtra during kharif 2023. The experiment was laid out in randomized block design with two replications. Analysis of variance revealed the existence of significant differences among genotypes for all characters studied. The correlation values indicate that, the characters number of branches per plant, number of pods per plant, kernel yield per plant, 100 kernel weight exhibited highly significant and positive correlation with pod yield concluding that the selection on the basis of phenotype of these characters will lead to high pod yield in groundnut. Path analysis showed highly positive direct effect of days to 50 per cent flowering, plant height, number of pods per plant, kernel yield per plant, 100 kernel weight were essential traits to be considered for realizing the improvement in groundnut.

Keywords: Groundnut, Correlation Coefficient, Path analysis.

Introduction

The groundnut (*Arachis hypogaea* L.) is the most important oilseed crop, commercially popular due to its superior quality of protein and edible oil. In Maharashtra, it is mainly grown as a kharif crop mostly under rainfed condition. Total world production of groundnut in 2022-23 account to approximately 38.6 million tons and it is currently grown about 21.8 million hectares worldwide. In India production of groundnut in 2023 was 6.73 million tones and major groundnut producing states are Gujarat, Rajasthan, Tamilnadu, Andhra Pradesh, Karnataka and Maharashtra (Anonymous 2023).

To step up the yield of groundnut per unit area per unit time, there is need to develop high yielding varieties with resistance to biotic and abiotic stresses. In fact, genotypic and phenotypic relationship of pod yield in groundnut with its component characters is helpful to determine the magnitude of the association among the variables and relative contribution of them on yield would be useful to plant breeder in developing an appropriate breeding strategy since pod yield per plant is complex character and is influenced by number of traits. Hence, selection of genotypes with desirable characters would be enhanced if significant correlation between yield and its component characters are established. Therefore, present study was undertaken to know the magnitude among yield traits and their direct and indirect effects towards pod yield.

Materials and Methods

The experimental material consists of 30 genotypes of groundnut. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with two replications during kharif, 2023 at Experimental Farm, College of Agriculture, Latur, Maharashtra. The plot size of 3.0 m x 0.60 m and each genotype is sown with spacing 30 cm between rows and 10 cm between the plants within rows. Recommended package of practices were followed in raising the crop. The observations were recorded on five randomly selected plants for quantitative traits viz., days to 50 per cent flowering, days to maturity, plant height, number of branches per plant, number of pods per plant, kernel yield per plant, 100 kernel weight, oil content, shelling percent, pod yield per plant and average values were used for statistical analysis (Panse and Sukhatme, 1979). Genotypic and phenotypic correlation coefficients were calculated using the method given by Johnson *et al.* (1955). The direct and indirect effects of the yield components on the yield were estimated by path coefficient analysis suggested by Wright (1921) and elaborated by Dewey and Lu (1959). The coefficients were obtained by solving the 'p' normal equations following the matrix given by Singh and Chaudhary (1977).

Result and Discussion

Analysis of variance is represented in (Table No.1) which revealed significant differences among the cultivars for most of the yield and yield contributing attributes. Significant differences were observed

among the 30 genotypes for all characters indicating the variation in the material studied for the most characters. Phenotypic coefficient of variation was found higher than genotypic coefficient of variation for all the traits indicating role of environment in expression of characters. Through the correlation and path analysis, the nature and extent of association between different characters influencing yield and causes of association can be better understood which helps in formulation of selection criteria for improvement of yield. In general, the genotypic correlation coefficients were higher than the phenotypic correlation coefficient which shows the high inherent association between the traits.

The correlation studies in (Table No.2) revealed that, the number of branches per plant, number of pods per plant, kernel yield per plant, 100 kernel weight exhibited significant positive correlation with pod yield per plant. Plant height and oil content showed positive but non-significant correlation with pod yield. The characters, number of days to 50 per cent flowering, branches per plant, number of pods per plant, kernel yield per plant and 100 kernel weight should be given more weightage in the selection process in the breeding programme aimed at improvement of pod yield per plant. The positive association of pod yield per plant with number of branches per plant, number of pods per plant, kernel yield per plant and 100 kernel weight was reported earlier by Mahalakshmi *et al.* (2005), Sawargaonkar *et al.* (2010), Thirumala Rao *et al.* (2014), Vasanthi *et al.* (2015), Meta and Monpara (2010) and Nirmla and Jayalakshmi (2015).

Path coefficient analysis represented in (Table No.3) showed high and positive significant direct effect on pod yield was exercised by days to 50 per cent flowering, plant height, number of pods per plant, kernel yield per plant and 100 kernel weight. Among these characters, number of pods per plant, kernel yield per plant and 100 kernel weight showed positive and significant correlation with pod yield. Highest negative direct effect was through days to maturity, number of branches per plant, shelling percent and oil content. These similar results also have been reported by Shrotri *et al.* (2021), Thirumala Rao (2016) and Babariya and Dobariya (2012).

Days to 50 per cent flowering exerted highest positive indirect effect through number of branches per plant. Days to maturity had significant positive indirect effect through number of branches per plant and kernel yield per plant. The trait, plant height had significant positive indirect effect through days to maturity, number of pods per plant, kernel yield per plant, shelling percentage and pod yield per plant. Number of branches per plant exerted positive significant indirect effect through days to maturity, plant height, number of pods per plant, kernel yield per plant, 100 kernel weight, shelling percent and pod yield per plant. Number of pods per plant had significant and positive indirect effect through days to maturity, plant height, kernel yield per plant, 100 kernel weight, shelling percentage and pod yield

per plant. Kernel yield per plant had significant and positive indirect effect through plant height, number of pods per plant, 100 kernel weight and pod yield per plant. Hundred kernel weight exerted positive significant indirect effect through plant height, number of pods per plant, kernel yield per plant and pod yield per plant. Oil content had significant positive indirect effect through days to maturity, plant height, number of pods per plant, kernel yield per plant, 100 kernel weight and pod yield per plant. Shelling percent had significant positive indirect effect through 100 kernel weight and oil content.

Conclusion

The selection of high yielding genotypes considering correlation and path coefficient analysis, the stress should be given on the traits number of pods per plant, kernel yield per plant and 100 kernel weight. The negative non-significant association of pod yield with the days to 50 per cent flowering, shelling percentage has to be broken through hybridization and selection of plants with high yield and moderately high shelling percentage and early flowering.

Table 1: ANOVA for yield and yield contributing traits in groundnut (*Arachis hypogaea* L.)

Source of Variation	Replication	Treatment	Error
DF	1	29	29
Days to 50 per cent flowering	-0.0285	27.06494**	0.48079
Days to maturity	12.00712	46.47520**	7.39165
Plant height(cm)	3.54550	36.37611**	3.27142
No. of branches per plant	0.04205	2.11929**	0.21096
No. of pods per plant(g)	4.00177	26.90403**	1.14287
Kernel yield per plant(g)	0.83982	28.16955**	0.51880
100 kernel weight(g)	0.60000	30.19310**	0.066897
Oil content (%)	0.10131	19.53455**	0.51124
Shelling percent (%)	25.45951	75.41549**	7.03721
Pod yield per plant (g)	0.76828	70.10228**	1.58868

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Table 2: Genotypic (rg) and phenotypic (rp) correlation coefficient among 10 characters in groundnut

Sr. No	Characters	R	Days to 50 % flowering	Days to maturity	Plant height (cm)	No of branches/plant	No of pods/plant	Kernel yield /plant(g)	100 kernel weight (g)	Oil content (%)	Shelling (%)	Pod yield /plant (g)
1.	Days to 50 % flowering	G	1.0000	0.9502	-0.3186	-0.2951	-0.4017	-0.1930	-0.1473	0.2194	0.2116	-0.3230
		P	1.0000	0.7892***	-0.3053*	-0.2569*	-0.3682**	-0.1748	-0.1348	-0.2003	0.2113	-0.2981*
2.	Days to maturity	G		1.0000	-0.1469	-0.2285	-0.1688	0.0783	-0.0251	-0.0429	0.2455	-0.0590
		P		1.0000	-0.1157	-0.1971	-0.1271	0.0939	-0.0019	-0.0429	0.1691	-0.0257
3.	Plant height (cm)	G			1.0000	0.2381	0.2792	0.1289	-0.0363	0.2378	-0.4231	0.2797
		P			1.0000	0.1749	0.2410	0.1140	-0.0165	0.1837	-0.3111*	0.2447
4.	No of branches/plant	G				1.0000	0.5785	0.4121	0.2517	0.0638	-0.1036	0.4134
		P				1.0000	0.4990***	0.3731**	0.2079	0.0721	-0.0894	0.3682**
5.	No of pods per plant	G					1.0000	0.9090	0.4111	0.1209	-0.1103	0.9370
		P					1.0000	0.8672**	0.4083**	0.1096	-0.0915	0.9046**
6.	Kernel yield/plant (g)	G						1.0000	0.4868	0.1890	0.1364	0.9432
		P						1.0000	0.4722***	0.1883	0.1371	0.9176**
7.	100 kernel weight (g)	G							1.0000	0.2375	0.4856	0.4238
		P							1.0000	0.2235	0.4331***	0.4174**
8.	Oil content (%)	G								1.0000	0.1044	0.1711
		P								1.0000	0.0808	0.1571
9.	Shelling (%)	G									1.0000	-0.1247
		P									1.0000	-0.1244
10.	Pod yield/Plant (g)	G										1.0000
		P										

*Significant at 5 % level, **Significant at 1 % level

Table 3: Genotypic path coefficient analysis showing direct and indirect effect of different characters on pod yield per plant in groundnut.

Sr.No	Characters		Days to 50 % flowering	Days to maturity	Plant height (cm)	No of Branches/plant	Number of pods /plant	Kernel yield /plant(g)	100 kernel weight (g)	Oil content (%)	Shelling (%)	Pod yield/plant (g)
1.	Days to 50 % flowering	G	0.2336	-0.2715	-0.0275	0.0274	-0.0340	-0.1821	-0.0149	-0.0019	-0.0521	-0.3230
		P	-0.0099	-0.0212	-0.0137	0.0195	-0.0884	-0.1263	-0.0128	0.0028	-0.0481	-0.2981
2.	Days to maturity	G	0.2220	-0.2857	-0.0127	0.0212	-0.0143	0.0739	-0.0025	-0.0004	-0.0605	-0.0590
		P	-0.0078	-0.0269	-0.0052	0.0150	-0.0305	0.0678	-0.0002	0.0006	-0.0385	-0.0257
3.	Plant height(cm)	G	-0.0744	0.0420	0.0863	-0.0221	0.0236	0.1217	-0.0037	0.0021	0.1043	0.2797
		P	0.0030	0.0031	0.0450	-0.0133	0.0579	0.0823	-0.0016	-0.0026	0.0708	0.2447
4.	No of Branches/plant	G	-0.0689	0.0653	0.0205	-0.0929	0.0489	0.3890	0.0254	0.0006	0.0255	0.4134
		P	0.0025	0.0053	0.0079	-0.0759	0.1198	0.2694	0.0198	-0.0010	0.0204	0.3682
5.	Number of pods /plant	G	-0.0938	0.0482	0.0241	-0.0537	0.0846	0.8579	0.0415	0.0010	0.0272	0.9370
		P	0.0037	0.0034	0.0108	-0.0379	0.2401	0.6263	0.0389	-0.0015	0.0208	0.9046
6.	Kernel yield /plant(g)	G	-0.0451	-0.0224	0.0111	-0.0383	0.0769	0.9438	0.0492	0.0016	-0.0336	0.9432
		P	0.0017	-0.0025	0.0051	-0.0283	0.2082	0.7223	0.0449	-0.0027	-0.0312	0.9176
7.	100 kernel weight (g)	G	-0.0344	0.0072	-0.0031	-0.0234	0.0348	0.4594	0.1010	0.0021	-0.1197	0.4238
		P	0.0013	0.0001	-0.0007	-0.0158	0.0980	0.3411	0.0952	-0.0032	-0.0986	0.4174
8.	Oil content (%)	G	-0.0513	0.0122	0.0205	-0.0059	0.0102	0.1783	0.0240	0.0087	-0.0257	0.1711
		P	0.0020	0.0012	0.0083	-0.0055	0.0263	0.1360	0.0213	-0.0141	-0.0184	0.1571
9.	Shelling (%)	G	0.0494	-0.0701	-0.0365	0.0096	-0.0093	0.1287	0.0490	0.0009	-0.2464	-0.1247
		P	-0.0021	-0.0045	-0.0045	-0.0140	0.0068	-0.0220	0.0990	0.0412	-0.0011	-0.2277

Diagonal entries (bold figures) are direct effects: off diagonal entries are indirect effects.